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MODELS FOR REGULATING GENDER EQUALITY IN LABOR RELATIONS

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Abstract: Gender equality is one of the fundamental principles for ensuring fairness and stability in labor relations. However, under modern economic and social conditions, achieving comprehensive gender equality requires the development of effective regulatory models and mechanisms. This article examines innovative approaches to regulating gender equality in labor relations, focusing on international experiences and gaps in national legislation. Additionally, it analyzes new legal mechanisms designed to strengthen gender equality and their impact on socio-economic stability.

Keywords: gender equality, labor relations, employee rights, employer interests, international standards, social justice, gender audit, regulatory models.

Gender equality plays a crucial role in safeguarding human rights, driving economic development, and enhancing societal stability. While many countries have enshrined this principle in their legislation, challenges remain in ensuring its full implementation in practice.

Today, various mechanisms have been developed to promote gender equality in labor relations, including gender audits, equal opportunity policies, and measures to combat gender-based discrimination in the workplace. However, the legislation in Uzbekistan still requires further refinement to effectively address issues related to gender equality.

To achieve gender equality in labor relations, a number of international and national standards have been established, providing a framework for the consistent implementation of this fundamental principle.

For example:

- The International Labour Organization (ILO) adopted the Equal Remuneration Convention, 1951 (No. 100), which was ratified by Uzbekistan on August 30, 1997 [1] va The International Labour Organization adopted the Discrimination (Employment and Occupation) Convention, 1958 (No. 111), which was ratified by Uzbekistan on August 30, 1997 [2].

- The European Union has adopted several directives aimed at strengthening gender equality, including the Directive 2006/54/EC on the

implementation of the principle of equal opportunities and equal treatment of men and women in matters of employment and occupation, and the Directive 2010/41/EU on equal treatment of self-employed men and women. These directives serve as key instruments in promoting gender equality across EU member states.[3].

- approaches to ensuring gender equality in labor relations in scandinavian countries. Scandinavian countries have adopted comprehensive approaches to integrating gender equality into labor relations. These nations successfully combine gender equality policies with social protection systems, ensuring a balance between professional and personal responsibilities for workers. The governments in countries like Sweden, Norway, and Denmark actively support gender equality not only through legislation but also by providing practical assistance and subsidies to employers and employees, promoting fairness and inclusion in the workplace.

Innovative regulatory models for gender equality in labor relations.

1. European Union (EU) Experience. The EU has implemented several laws and directives to ensure gender equality in labor relations. Among them, the Directive 2006/54/EC mandates the elimination of workplace discrimination and encourages the use of gender audits to identify disparities in wages and opportunities. This structured approach aims to address and reduce gender-based inequalities across member states.

2. Scandinavian Model. The Scandinavian model merges gender equality with robust social protection policies. These countries ensure gender parity not only through comprehensive legal frameworks but also by actively supporting families through subsidies, childcare services, and paid parental leave. Such measures help mitigate the challenges of combining work and personal life, ensuring a more equitable labor environment.

3. French Experience. France employs an innovative incentive-based mechanism to promote gender equality. Employers demonstrating active efforts to ensure gender balance in the workplace receive tax benefits. This system acts as a strong motivator for businesses to adopt and implement gender equality practices, creating a more inclusive and fair labor market.

These models illustrate how international practices can provide actionable frameworks for advancing gender equality in labor relations. Adapting such approaches to national contexts can foster a more equitable and inclusive working environment for all.

Ensuring gender equality is vital for the sustainable development of a nation. Achieving gender equality in labor relations can be accomplished through the study of international best practices and the enhancement of national legislation. By implementing effective mechanisms in practice, a more balanced relationship between employers and employees can be established. This not only drives economic growth but also promotes greater social justice.

Currently, based on the experiences of foreign countries, the following four models for achieving gender equality have been identified [4] :

Gender Integration Model. The gender integration model encompasses all aspects of economic and societal life and is widely implemented in countries such as Denmark, Iceland, Norway, Sweden, and Finland. This model aims to create a fair environment by integrating the principle of gender equality into all areas of policy-making. It emphasizes making equality a fundamental part of social life. The core principles of this model include:

- Policy integration: Incorporating gender equality into all levels of policy-making.

- Equal opportunities: Ensuring equal opportunities for men and women in social and economic life.

- Reducing economic disparities: Addressing and eliminating gender gaps in the economy.

- Work-life balance: Promoting policies that help individuals balance family and professional responsibilities.

- Cultural transformation: Shifting societal norms and values to include gender equality as an integral part of social standards.

Through these principles, gender equality becomes deeply embedded within social norms and cultural values.

Intersectionality Model. The intersectionality model is based on policies of affirmative action and is predominantly applied in European countries, including France, Belgium, and Spain. Each of these countries implements unique approaches to gender equality. For instance, in France, initiatives regarding gender issues typically originate from civil society and are directed toward state institutions, while in Belgium, such initiatives are driven by state institutions and extended to society. Belgium has established specific roles and advisory councils dedicated to promoting gender equality. In France, the High Council for Gender Equality plays a pivotal role in coordinating efforts in this field. The core principles of this model include:

- Affirmative action policies: Developing policies aimed at creating equal opportunities for men and women. This approach involves implementing targeted measures to reduce gender disparities in society.

- Civil society and state coordination: Gender equality initiatives are synchronized between civil society and state institutions, ensuring collaboration and alignment. Each country's unique approach strengthens this partnership.

- Institutional support: Establishing institutions responsible for ensuring equal participation of men and women in political and social life.

This model demonstrates how affirmative action and collaboration between civil society and governmental institutions can effectively address gender disparities and promote equality.

Beyond gender equality model. The beyond gender equality model goes beyond addressing only gender disparities and considers other factors such as age, social status, and ethnicity (e.g., in the United Kingdom). This approach highlights the interconnection between economic development and gender equality. It emphasizes creating new opportunities for women during periods of economic growth, increasing their participation in business and entrepreneurship, and ensuring equal access to education and healthcare services. These efforts aim to balance gender relations and foster inclusivity.

Collaborative Support Model. The collaborative support model represents a new approach formed through initiatives from both "bottom-up" (women's organizations and community-driven efforts) and "top-down" (international organizations and financial resource-driven demands). This model seeks to achieve gender equality by promoting cooperation between the state and civil society. Non-governmental organizations play an active role in this process, enhancing social partnership and strengthening collaborative frameworks.

In conclusion, ensuring gender equality is not only a fundamental criterion for protecting human rights but also a critical foundation for fostering efficiency, stability, and social justice in labor relations. Legislation and mechanisms developed based on international standards and best practices provide the framework for implementing gender equality in practice. Tools such as gender audits are instrumental in identifying existing challenges and taking actionable measures to address them. As a result, balanced relationships between employees and employers are established, contributing to economic growth and societal stability.

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Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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